

APPROACHES TO THE CLUSTER SYSTEM IN EDUCATION

Omila Odilovna Yuldasheva

Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute

1st year Master's degree of foreign languages and literature

E-mail: omilayuldasheva9@gmail.com

Supervisor **Nasirova Umida Kamolovna** PhD in philosophy

Uzbek State World Languages University

ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to implementation of the cluster approach to education, understanding the concept of cluster, being able to correctly apply it in education and integrating educational institutions.

Key words: *cluster, implementation, education, effectively.*

Introduction

The cluster approach in education makes it possible to act effectively and successfully, bearing in mind the priority perspective common to all partners, it is advisable to coordinate educational activities. Such as partnerships which take place in community, this type of activity that makes it possible to provide more effective assistance to members of each group, strive to remain different from each other, to recognize the differences of individuals and organizations.

In the context of the emerging innovative type of economy, local universities are faced with the acute problem of introducing innovations that can make universities more competitive and form a positive national competitiveness. The modern education system has been in constant reform and renewal in recent years.

The rapidity with which clusters and the policies associated with them have firmly entered the economic circulation has not given time for well-founded answers to questions about their essence and role in economic development. Clusters, depending on the context, mean many different structures, and the proposed mechanisms for supporting clustering processes are characterized by an extremely general nature and combine a wide range of traditional development policies. In practice, this often leads to non-obviousness and inefficiency of cluster policy measures, unpredictable, often opposite to the expected reaction of a complex object of regulation. Therefore, the formation of the cluster concept as a scientifically and practically proven approach should be preceded by an understanding of this concept and related phenomena¹. According to Volchok's opinion the concept of cluster in education is a complex process, but it is a phenomenon which can be formed in a practical approach.

It is generally accepted that clusters act as a means of increasing the competitiveness of territories, the transition to production processes with greater added value, and contribute to the establishment of constructive relationships between enterprises, research, educational, financial institutions and authorities. The cluster approach radically changes the content of regional and industrial policy, since the efforts of the authorities are directed to the development of a system of relationships between economic entities and state institutions.

The concept of "cluster" first gained its fame in economics in the 80s of the XX century, where it was first used in economic theory by Michael Porter. Here, a detailed description of the cluster formation mechanism was given as "a community of firms, closely related industries, mutually contributing to the growth of each other's competitiveness". M. Porter, as a popularize of the definition of an economic cluster, showed that: "The competitiveness of a company is largely determined by the

¹ Волчок Т. И. Профессионально-образовательный кластер как форма социального партнерства в подготовке кадров // Научно-методический электронный журнал «Концепт». – 2017. – Т. 25. – С. 18–20. – URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2017/770484.htm>.

competitiveness of its economic environment, which, in turn, depends on the basic conditions (common resource) and competition within the cluster².

A cluster is a combination of several homogeneous elements, which can be considered as an independent unit with certain properties. A cluster is a group of neighboring interconnected companies and related organizations operating in a certain area, characterized by a common activity and complementary to each other. A cluster is a group of geographically localized interconnected companies, suppliers of equipment, components, specialized services, infrastructure, research institutes, higher educational institutions and other organizations that complement each other and enhance the competitive advantages of individual companies and the cluster as a whole.³

According to this outlook, an educational cluster is a set of interconnected institutions of vocational education united by industry and partnerships with industry enterprises; it is a learning system mutual learning and self-learning tools in the innovation chain.

Cluster training is a relatively new direction in professional pedagogy, its introduction into the training process requires the definition of pedagogical conditions and experimental verification of the effectiveness of the formation of a competent specialist. In other words, first you need to prepare a professional teacher who will train students - future specialists. The role of the university in the cluster is reduced to producing innovative goods. What does this mean in practice? Research institutes and industrial establishments of the region become the base of practices and get the opportunity to participate in the formation of a specialist on their own scientific and educational base, in accordance with their needs and development prospects. The cluster as a mechanism for innovative management of the development of the general education system makes it possible to ensure the effectiveness of the activities of each

² Michael Porter. Competiton,competitive, advantage and clusters.

³ Громько Ю.В. Что такое кластеры и как их создавать? // Альманах «Восток». – 2007. – Вып. 1 [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: URL: http://www.situation.ru/app/j_ artp_ 1178.htm.

educational institution included in it, including: partnership, attraction of non-budgetary funds in the field of education, the emergence of resources for innovative training, retraining and advanced training of teaching staff, qualitatively new results of education based on the continuous development of the child, can improve the appearance of institutions⁴.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that it is assumed that the concept of cluster was first founded in the sphere of economy, and now it is aimed at implementation in almost all areas, and it is expected to achieve the intended results by using it effectively in education.

REFERENCE LIST

1. *Википедия Свободная энциклопедия [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: URL: <http://ru.Wikipedia.org/wiki>.*
2. *Волчок Т. И. Профессионально-образовательный кластер как форма социального партнерства в подготовке кадров // Научно-методический электронный журнал «Концепт». – 2017. – Т. 25. – С. 18–20. – URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2017/770484.htm>.*
3. *Громыко Ю.В. Что такое кластеры и как их создавать? // Альманах «Восток». – 2007. – Вып. 1 [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: URL: http://www.situation.ru/app/j_artp_1178.htm.*
4. *Руднева П.С. Опыт создания структурных кластеров в развитых странах // Экономика региона. – 2007. – № 18. – Ч. 2 (декабрь).*
5. *Трещевский Ю.И., Исаева Е.М., Мовсесова М.Г. Управление эффективностью организаций на основе интеграции // Вестник ВГУ. – 2008. – № 2. – С. 13–20. – (Экономика и управление).*
6. *Трушников Д.Ю., Трушникова В.И. Воспитание в условиях университетского кластера и ценностные студенчества [Электронный ресурс].*

⁴ Трушников Д.Ю., Трушникова В.И. Воспитание в условиях университетского кластера и ценностные студенчества [Электронный ресурс].